

DPsim - A Dynamic Phasor Real-Time Simulator for Power Systems

Markus Mirz, Steffen Vogel, Georg Reinke, Antonello Monti

*Institute for Automation of Complex Power Systems, RWTH Aachen University,
Aachen, Germany*

Abstract

DPsim is a real-time capable solver for power systems that operates in the dynamic phasor and electromagnetic transient (EMT) domain. This solver primarily targets co-simulation applications and large-scale scenarios since dynamic phasors do not require sampling rates as high as EMT simulations do. Due to the frequency shift introduced by the dynamic phasor approach, the sampling rate and rate of data exchange between simulators can be reduced. DPsim supports the Common Information Model (CIM) format for the description of electrical network topology, component parameters and power flow data and it is closely integrated with the VILLASframework to support a wide range of interfaces for co-simulation. Simulation examples demonstrate the accuracy of DPsim and its real-time performance for increasing system sizes.

Keywords: Real-Time Simulation, Dynamic Phasors, Co-Simulation

1. Motivation and significance

DPsim introduces the dynamic phasor (DP) approach to real-time power system simulation. The motivation is to remove the requirement of proportionality between the simulation time step and the highest frequency of simulated signals. Especially for power electronics and geographically distributed real-time simulation, this is an interesting feature. Currently, the focus of DPsim is more on the application in distributed real-time co-simulation than power electronics. The idea is that the larger the simulation step, the smaller the impact of the communication delay between simulators, which are geographically distributed.

Distributed real-time co-simulation is motivated by large system simulations requiring more simulation capacity than is locally available and by the possibility of Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) testing with hardware under

14 test and simulators at different locations. Using dynamic phasors for this
15 application is a fairly recent development although the dynamic phasor, or
16 the envelope function concept, is well known and was introduced in power
17 electronics analysis in [1] as a generalized state space averaging method.

18 The authors of [2] have developed a distributed real-time simulation lab-
19 oratory by applying a communication platform as a simulator-to-simulator
20 interface in order to enable remote and online monitoring of interconnected
21 transmission and distribution systems. Each simulator carries out simula-
22 tions in time domain, while the variables exchanged at the interconnected
23 nodes, i.e. decoupling point, are in the form of time-varying Fourier coeffi-
24 cients. The electromagnetic transient (EMT) values cannot be exchanged at
25 every simulation step due to the communication delay. This delay may be
26 directly incorporated into the physical power system model using travelling
27 wave transmission line models [3]. However, electromagnetic waves travel
28 about 15 km in 50 μ s, a time which equals the typical step time in real-time
29 EMT power system simulation. This means that a communication delay in
30 the range of milliseconds would have to be compensated with a line length of
31 several hundred kilometers which may require large and unrealistic changes
32 to the original system model. Therefore, this method is suited for appli-
33 cations on local simulation clusters where the delay is only few simulation
34 steps, but not for internet-distributed simulation, where the expected delay
35 is often tens of milliseconds. In the latter case, the insertion of a transmission
36 line model with the required parameters into the model would have a severe
37 impact on the behavior of the system. Without compensation, the commu-
38 nication delay might cause large errors and even instability of the simulation
39 as shown in [4] for a delay of more than 30 ms.

40 Starting from the concept presented in [2], we propose interfaces and
41 system-wide simulation state variables based on dynamic phasors. This ap-
42 proach has two benefits explained in [5], which presents a comparison of DP
43 and EMT simulations conducted in DPsim. First, it takes advantage of the
44 computational efficiency of dynamic phasors in scenarios that involve band-
45 pass signals with large center frequencies, as in the case of switching power
46 electronics. Secondly, it increases the simulation time step thus reducing the
47 difference between the local simulation time step size and the round trip time
48 between simulators.

49 The approach employed in [2] requires the extraction of phasor informa-
50 tion from the EMT signals. Therefore, the transparency of the interface is
51 not guaranteed since the interface algorithm may alter the exchanged sig-
52 nals. This extraction step is eliminated by using dynamic phasors as state
53 variables. Because of these features, DPsim is now part of the distributed
54 real-time co-simulation platform described in [6], which is also the base for

55 the experiment described in [2]. A first example of distributed real-time co-
56 simulation using DPsim is presented in [7]. This example shows the impact
57 of the latency in geographical distributed simulation on the results and how
58 the latency can be modelled a priori to running actual simulations.

59 Besides, there are other relevant open-source initiatives in the field of
60 power system simulation to be mentioned. In particular the Modelica com-
61 munity is very active in adapting Modelica environments for large scale power
62 system cases [8, 9] and providing comprehensive libraries of models [10, 11].
63 These initiatives aim to enable large scale, fast simulation of power systems
64 using open-source components but the focus is slightly different compared
65 to the work presented here. The primary objective of DPsim is to assure
66 a deterministic time step in terms of simulated and computation time to
67 provide real-time capability required for Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) exper-
68 iments. This is why in DPsim higher order solver methods are avoided and
69 the system is split into subsystems, which are solved separately. The afore-
70 mentioned related work does not seem to rely on such compromises since a
71 deterministic time step is not required. While Modelica allows a convenient
72 definition of physical models, DPsim does not intend to provide a solution
73 in this regard. The idea is rather to extend the set of available models in
74 DPsim by generating C-code from Modelica models to represent components
75 connected to the network. These can be linked to DPsim and solved by the
76 ODE solver that was integrated into DPsim for this purpose.

77 Another related work which is not open-source but also DP based is de-
78 scribed in [12]. Similarly to DPsim, the authors have developed a simulator
79 based on the DP approach. However, the focus does not seem to be fast sim-
80 ulation or real-time simulation since the simulator was developed in Python
81 and there are no measures described in order to speed up the simulation.
82 Furthermore, the validation is focusing on the correctness of the simulation
83 rather than simulation speed.

84 **2. Software description**

85 The main theoretical building blocks of DPsim are the dynamic phasor
86 concept and the modified nodal analysis (MNA). Dynamic phasors [13] have
87 various names in scientific literature. Depending on the field and applica-
88 tion, they are known as generalized averaging method [1], shifted frequency
89 analysis [14], equivalent envelope [15, 16] or baseband signal [17]. Here, the
90 term dynamic phasors is selected because it is widely known in the power
91 system community. The basic idea of dynamic phasors is to approximate a

92 time domain signal x with a Fourier series representation as shown in (1)

$$x(\tau) = \sum_k X_k(t) e^{jk\omega_s(\tau)} \quad (1)$$

93 where $\tau \in (t - T, t]$. The k^{th} coefficient is determined by

$$X_k(t) = \langle x \rangle_k(t) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t-T}^t x(\tau) e^{-jk\omega_s(\tau)} d\tau \quad (2)$$

94 where ω_s is the fundamental system frequency and $k\omega_s$ are its harmonics.

95 MNA is used for the representation of the network as a linear equation
96 system, whereas complex components, such as electrical machines, connected
97 to the network are treated by a separate ODE solver. Depending on the simu-
98 lation scenario, the admittance matrices of the required network topologies
99 can be pre-processed, i.e. factorized, before simulation start to guarantee a
100 deterministic simulation time step.

101 The simulation kernel of DPsim is extended with interfaces to support
102 different use cases such as circuit or system simulation, batch simulation,
103 co-simulation and HIL testing. DPsim supports the Common Information
104 Model (CIM) [18] as native input for the description of electrical network
105 topologies, component parameters and load flow data, which is used for ini-
106 tialization. Users can interact with the simulation kernel via Python bind-
107 ings, which can be used to script the execution, schedule events, change pa-
108 rameters and retrieve results. Python scripts have been proven an easy and
109 flexible way to codify the complete workflow of a simulation from modelling
110 to analysis and plotting, for example in Jupyter notebooks using Numpy and
111 Matplotlib. Furthermore, DPsim supports co-simulation and interfaces to
112 a variety of communication protocols of commercial hardware via the inte-
113 gration of DPsim with the *VILLASframework* [19], that enables large-scale
114 co-simulations and HIL experiments.

115 2.1. Software Architecture

116 2.1.1. Module Structure

117 The DPsim simulation kernel and its component models are implemented
118 in the C++ programming language. The availability of good compilers and
119 highly optimized software libraries, such as *Eigen* [20], *Sundials* [21] and
120 *VILLASnode*, which is part of the VILLASframework, for C++ were key
121 factors for this decision.

122 The core of DPsim consists of models and solvers as depicted in Figure
123 1. Interfaces to other software, hardware or data are supported through
124 external libraries. Grid data in CIM standard format is imported using the

Figure 1: Overview of DPsim’s main components and dependencies on external libraries

125 *CIM++* library [22]. Communication with other software, e.g. real-time
 126 simulators, control and monitoring software, as well as hardware is provided
 127 by the VILLAS framework. For linear algebra operations, DPsim uses the
 128 Eigen library. The MNA solver of DPsim uses the Eigen LU factorization
 129 and *Eigen::Dense/Sparse::Matrix* are the standard data types for all matrix
 130 variables. The Sundials solver package is included in DPsim to provide more
 131 complex ODE solvers for components connected to the network.

132 Compilation from source code requires a Git, a C++11 compiler and
 133 CMake 3.6. Tested compilers are Clang, GCC, MSVC and Intel’s ICC. As a
 134 base operating system Ubuntu 18.04 LTS or Fedora 29 are recommended. For
 135 real-time execution an a Linux 4.9 kernel with the *PREEMPT_RT* patch-set
 136 is recommended.

137 2.1.2. Class Hierarchy

138 *Simulation* is the main interface class for users to control the simulation
 139 state. The attributes of a *Simulation* instance hold all the information that
 140 specifies one simulation scenario in DPsim. The *Simulation* holds references
 141 to the solvers, interfaces and the power system model information. This
 142 hierarchy is presented in Figure 2. The complete class hierarchy diagram
 143 can be found in the developer’s documentation of DPsim [23]. All solvers
 144 inherit from *Solver*, e.g. *MNASolver* and *ODESolver*, and all interfaces from
 145 *Interface*, e.g. for VILLASnode. All component models, power system, signal
 146 etc., derive from the class *IdentifiedObject*. The main attribute of this class
 147 is a unique identifier, which is equivalent to the *mRID* in CIM.

Figure 2: Diagram of the main classes of DPsim

148 2.1.3. Parallelization

149 In order to utilize the multiple processor cores of modern computer sys-
 150 tems and speed up the simulation, the computation of one time step is split
 151 up into multiple tasks. These tasks are defined by the various parts of the
 152 simulation (like instances of *Solver* and *Interface*). An internal scheduler
 153 creates a task graph by analyzing which variables are modified and used by
 154 the tasks. This task graph is a directed acyclic graph with nodes represent-
 155 ing tasks and edges representing data dependencies. The scheduler uses this
 156 graph to distribute the tasks onto multiple threads such that these depen-
 157 dencies are upheld. DPsim implements different scheduling algorithms for
 158 this purpose, the simplest of which being level scheduling as used in [24].
 159 This algorithm divides the tasks into ordered levels such that each task only
 160 depends on tasks in a previous level. To simulate a time step, these levels
 161 are then executed in order by distributing all tasks of one level evenly among
 162 the available threads.

163 To further optimize the simulation performance for large networks when
 164 using multiple processors, a decoupling transmission line model can be in-
 165 troduced. In this model a transmission line is represented using equivalent
 166 current sources and resistances at the line ends that are not topologically
 167 connected as described in [25, ch. 6.2]. Instead, the ends are indirectly con-
 168 nected by updating the values of the sources based on the values on the other
 169 end only after a delay τ , which depends on the line's parameters. As subsys-
 170 tems that are connected using this line model are not connected in a strict
 171 topological sense, they can be solved independently and in parallel. This
 172 significantly reduces the computational effort to simulate large systems.

173 2.2. Software Functionalities

174 DPsim supports both dynamic phasor and EMT simulation. Further-
 175 more, DPsim is optimized for real-time simulation but it is also possible to

176 run the same simulation scenario offline meaning that the simulation is ex-
177 ecuted as fast as possible. These different simulation modes are compatible
178 with the user and simulation interface which are covered in the following.

179 *2.2.1. User Interface*

180 Network models can be directly defined in the C++ code. This technique
181 is complemented by a CIM importer, which allows the user to directly load
182 network models from CIM-XML files. This proves to be an adequate form
183 to describe network topology and component parameters, which are required
184 by the solver. This CIM importer relieves the user from defining the model
185 in plain C++ code. However, CIM-XML is not suitable for the definition of
186 more complex simulation scenarios with time varying parameters or topol-
187 ogy changes caused by contingencies in the system (e.g. breaker events or
188 faults). Therefore, DPsim features Python bindings to most parts of the
189 C++ programming interface. A scripting language like Python is used to
190 define scenarios by leveraging the flexibility of a general purpose imperative
191 language. This allows the user to write a single Python script to:

- 192 • Describe the network topology and parameters
- 193 • Load a network from CIM data and optionally extend it
- 194 • Define a simulation scenario with events or parameter changes
- 195 • Execute the simulation and analyze or plot the simulation results

196 *2.2.2. Simulation Interface*

197 Interfacing the simulation kernel is desirable for multiple reasons:

- 198 • Real-time exchange of simulation signals for co-simulation or HIL test-
199 ing
- 200 • User interface for online monitoring and control of the simulation
- 201 • Logging of simulation results for offline analysis
- 202 • Import of time series data, for example load and production profiles

203 For commercial simulation tools these interfaces are a major selling point
204 as new protocols and standards and DAQ cards are introduced continuously.
205 Their implementation and maintenance is time consuming and seemingly
206 never ending. By design, DPsim tries to avoid this pitfall by leaving the im-
207 plementation of interfaces, data formats and protocols to a separate project.

Figure 3: VILLASnode as a gateway for distributed co-simulation with DPsim.

208 VILLASnode, a component of the VILLASframework project, handles in-
 209 put/output as well as translation between different protocols. DPsim fo-
 210 cuses on solving the system model and provides only a single type of interface,
 211 shared memory, to the VILLASnode gateway. Interfaces to external systems,
 212 databases, files or the web interface are then handled by the wide range of
 213 supported interfaces of the VILLASnode gateway, which in this case acts as a
 214 proxy between the shared-memory interface to DPsim and the outside world.
 215 Responsibilities are clearly separated. This allows the development of new
 216 interfaces without having to modify the simulation kernel itself.

217 In addition, DPsim can use the VILLASnode interfaces for co-simulation
 218 with other simulators or remote DPsim instances. In such a scenario, DPsim
 219 is usually coupled using an Ideal Transformer Model (ITM). Figure 3 shows
 220 a decoupled model, which exchanges voltages in one and currents signals in
 221 the opposite direction to control respective sources. For a phasor simulation,
 222 the exchanged signals are complex-valued attributes which are passed via
 223 the shared-memory interface to VILLASnode which further sends them to a
 224 remote simulator using one of VILLAS' supported protocols (e.g. MQTT,
 225 UDP, ZeroMQ, ...). For geographically distributed simulations, VILLASnode
 226 can implement interface algorithms to compensate for the inherent commu-
 227 nication latencies when executed in real-time over a high latency connection
 228 such as the internet. Alternatively, the implementation of a Discrete Fourier
 229 Transform (DFT) in VILLASnode allows for a coupling of the phasor-based
 230 DPsim with other EMT-based simulation tools like OPAL-RT or RTDS.

231 DPsim exchanges simulation data with the VILLASnode gateway via a
 232 shared-memory region. The execution of DPsim and VILLASnode as inde-
 233 pendent processes is crucial in real-time simulation scenarios as the main
 234 simulation kernel must not be interrupted by background activities such as
 235 data logging to a possibly blocking database.

236 Furthermore, DPsim has its own simple logging module to write results
 237 to CSV files for archival and post processing. This method is easy to setup
 238 and convenient for small simulations where post processing and analysis of
 239 simulation results is done in MATLAB or Python. In the long term, the

240 internal CSV logging functionality is planned to be incorporated into VIL-
241 LASnode and enhanced by the support of additional data formats like HDF5
242 as used by MATLAB.

243 **3. Implementation and Empirical Results**

244 To complement the previous overview of DPsim’s architecture, the next
245 subsection explains implementation specifics affecting the real-time perfor-
246 mance of DPsim. The real-time performance of DPsim is demonstrated in
247 the following subsection. The remaining two subsections demonstrate the
248 correctness of the solution computed by DPsim and its real-time capability.
249 The first simulation validates only the network solution, which is computed
250 by the MNA solver against Matlab Simulink. The second simulation features
251 a combination of the MNA solver for the network solution and an ODE solver
252 for the numerical integration of the synchronous generator equations.

253 *3.1. Implementation Details*

254 Only a compiled language like C++ with minimal runtime overhead is
255 suitable for the implementation since DPsim is targeting simulation time
256 steps in the range of milliseconds to microseconds on off the shelf computing
257 hardware. Great care was taken to avoid memory allocation during the actual
258 simulation. Whenever possible, DPsim utilizes low order integration methods
259 and avoids iterative solver strategies to minimize computation time. That is
260 why the network part is handled by the MNA solver specifically developed
261 for DPsim.

262 DPsim is compatible with Windows, macOS and Linux operating sys-
263 tems. Eventually, the operating system configuration can have a large im-
264 pact on the real-time performance. To guarantee real-time execution, DP-
265 sim leverages several Linux real-time features such as the real-time capable
266 *SCHED_FIFO* scheduler, real-time signals, the *timerfd* interface, or control
267 groups (*cgroups*). Many of these features are nowadays incorporated in the
268 standard Linux kernel but have their origin in the *PREEMPT_RT* patch-set.
269 The patch-set is slowly integrated into the mainline kernel but still exists
270 and can be applied to further improve the real-time performance by enabling
271 preemption of critical sections such as interrupt handlers. The capability to
272 preempt critical sections in the operating system kernel reduces the overall
273 system latency and therefore helps onto strict dead-lines at each time-step
274 interval.

275 Real-time execution on Windows or macOS is not supported. Best real-
276 time performance was achieved on a recent Intel x86_64 multi-core machine
277 with optimized BIOS settings to avoid interruptions of the system by the

278 System Management Mode (SMM). To do so, DPsim execution threads are
279 isolated from remaining system processes using Linux’s *cgroup* feature. This
280 reduces the impact of background jobs in the system on the real-time per-
281 formance.

282 As a good start for real-time optimizations, we recommend Redhat’s Real-
283 time Guide [26] with its *tuned* tool and the *realtime* profile. An updated list
284 of optimization options can be found in the DPsim documentation [23].

285 To control the time step, DPsim is using *timerfd* interface in Linux en-
286 vironments. The *timerfd* interface allows for the configuration repetitive
287 interval and one-off timers. It uses blocking file descriptors to suspend the
288 execution of the simulation loop until the beginning of the next interval. This
289 approach is more efficient than the use of the more common *timer* interface,
290 which relies on signals. At the same time, *timerfd* is more accurate as calls
291 to *sleep* or *nanosleep* as they suffer of a lingering drift to non-equidistant
292 execution intervals. The *timerfd* is also used to schedule the synchronized
293 start of distributed simulations as described in the introduction.

294 Shared-memory is a common method for inter-process communication
295 (IPC) used on symmetric multi-processing (SMP) machines. It enables user
296 processes to exchange data without the involvement of the OS kernel. Shared-
297 memory IPC allows both processes, the solver and the gateway, to be exe-
298 cuted in parallel while streaming their data with minimal latency over a
299 queue in the shared memory region. The queue is implemented as a lock free
300 multiple producer/multiple consumer (MPMC) queue and relies on atomic
301 operations of the processor to facilitate synchronization of the DPsim and
302 VILLASnode processes. The lockfree queue is a thread safe data structure.
303 It is used to pass samples of simulation data between the involved processes.
304 As such *message passing* is used as the main paradigm to avoid data races.
305 During the initialization phase, semaphores are used to avoid race conditions
306 in the setup of the shared-memory regions. The absence of the operating sys-
307 tem in the communication is crucial to avoid costly context switches, which
308 have to be avoided in a real-time context. Using the shared-memory interface,
309 the DPsim simulation loop can run uninterrupted in a high priority process.
310 At the same time, VILLASnode gets assigned a lower priority for handling
311 of possibly blocking disk or database accesses. In a hardware-in-the-loop
312 simulation it might be necessary to have hard real-time capable interfaces
313 to the real world. For this purpose, DPsim supports an arbitrary number of
314 shared-memory interfaces at the same time. This allows the user to configure
315 one VILLASnode process with a high priority for the control of PCIe FPGA
316 or DAQ cards, and at the same time another VILLASnode process for low
317 priority logging of simulation data in the background.

Figure 4: WSCC 9-bus system (a) and average wall clock time per step (b).

3.2. Real-Time Performance Evaluation

DPsim is specifically designed for real-time simulation. To assess the effect of system size on the real-time performance of DPsim, a simple test network was copied multiple times and connected with additional transmission lines. Figure 4a shows the WSCC 9-bus system, which was used for this purpose. The copies were connected in a ring-like topology using additional transmission lines at the nodes 5, 6, and 8. The average wall clock time needed to simulate one time step was measured for a simulation time period of 0.1 s with a time step of 100 μ s. Each measurement was further averaged over ten simulations of the same system. The measurements were performed on a system running Ubuntu 16.04 on an Intel Xeon Silver 4114 processor featuring ten cores clocked at 2.2 GHz. The results are shown in figure 4b for two different configurations: For the normal simulation, the additional transmission lines were modelled using the Pi model and only one thread was used. For the parallel simulation, the decoupling transmission line model was used for the additional lines and ten threads were employed. As it can be seen, the use of multiple threads and the special transmission line model greatly reduces the wall clock time necessary for simulating a single time step. Even for 40 copies of the original system (resulting in a system size of 360 nodes), the wall clock time per step stays under the simulation time step of 100 μ s, thus allowing for real-time simulation. For a small number of system copies, DPsim supports simulation time steps of about 10 μ s, which is a typical time step for commercial EMT simulators. However, it should be noted that such small time steps are not the aim of DPsim since the simulation is conducted in DP and not EMT.

Figure 5: Example circuit (a) and DPsim dynamic phasor and Simulink EMT simulation results for node 1 (b)

3.3. Validation of the MNA Network Solver

The next simulation case demonstrates the accuracy of the MNA network solver compared to Simulink results. Both simulators DPsim and Simulink are run with a simulation time step of $100 \mu\text{s}$. It can be seen that for such small time steps DP simulations yield the same results as EMT. The larger the time step, the more will the results degrade. It is shown in [5] that the degradation of the results with larger time steps is smaller when using the DP approach compared to EMT.

Figure 5a shows the simulated circuit, which is composed of one current source of 10 A, two resistors of 1Ω , an inductor of 1 mH and a capacitor of 1 mF. The voltage source is set to its nonzero peak value at the beginning because it is following a cosine with zero phase shift. Therefore, the system is not starting from steady-state and a transient can be observed. The DPsim dynamic phasor results are transformed to time domain values and compared against Simulink EMT results. As can be seen from Figure 5b, the results match.

3.4. Validation of the ODE Solver for Components

The following example compares the results of Simulink and DPsim for a three phase synchronous generator fault. Here, the simulation time step is $50 \mu\text{s}$ for DPsim and Simulink. As in the previous simulation case, the DP approach would allow for larger time steps than EMT. A comprehensive study investigating this property and featuring synchronous generator models is presented in [27]. Initially, the load is 300 MW and the fault is applied at 0.1 s. The generator parameters are taken from example 3.1 in [28]. As

Figure 6: Diagram of the main classes of DPsim

367 in the previous example, the dynamic phasor results are transformed to time
 368 domain values before the comparison. Again, it is visible that the DPsim
 369 results match the Simulink results except when the fault is cleared. In con-
 370 trast to DPsim, the fault in Simulink is not immediately cleared but at the
 371 next zero-crossing.

372 4. Illustrative Examples

373 As mentioned in Section 2.2, there are two ways to define a circuit topol-
 374 ogy for DPsim: coding the topology using the Python or C++ or importing
 375 it from CIM. The two options are presented by means of two examples: a
 376 circuit and a small power system. The first example presented in this section
 377 demonstrates the definition utilizing Python while the second example takes
 378 advantage of the CIM import function.

379 4.1. Defining a Circuit Simulation in Python

380 The circuit of the previous section, Figure 5, is taken as an example to
 381 demonstrate how circuits can be defined using DPsim's Python interface.
 382 The topology can be created in Python as depicted by Listing 1.

Listing 1: Python code to define a circuit.

```
383 # Nodes
384 gnd = dpsim.dp.Node.GND()
385 n1 = dpsim.dp.Node('n1')
386 n2 = dpsim.dp.Node('n2')
```

```

387
388     # Components
389     cs = dpsim.dp.ph1.CurrentSource('cs')
390     cs.I.ref = complex(10,0)
391     r1 = dpsim.dp.ph1.Resistor('r_1')
392     r1.R = 1
393     c1 = dpsim.dp.ph1.Capacitor('c_1')
394     c1.C = 0.001
395     l1 = dpsim.dp.ph1.Inductor('l_1')
396     l1.L = 0.001
397     r2 = dpsim.dp.ph1.Resistor('r_2')
398     r2.R = 1
399
400     # Connections
401     cs.connect([gnd, n1])
402     r1.connect([n1, gnd])
403     c1.connect([n1, n2]);
404     l1.connect([n2, gnd]);
405     r2.connect([n2, gnd]);
406
407     system = dpsim.SystemTopology(50, [gnd, n1, n2], [cs, r1, c1, l1, r2]);
408     sim = dpsim.Simulation('circuit', system, timestep=0.0001, duration=0.1)
409     sim.start()

```

410 First, the nodes and components are declared and parameterized. Then, the
411 connections between components and nodes are set and in the following step
412 all network objects are added to the system topology. Finally, the system
413 topology and parameters such as time step and final time can be used to
414 create a simulation instance, which can be started, stopped and stepped
415 through. Optionally, initial voltages could be assigned to the nodes. Since
416 this is not the case here, the initial voltages are set to zero.

417 4.2. Simulating a Power System defined in CIM

418 The next example presents the CIM loading functionality, which is used
419 to read the data of the WSCC 9-bus system as displayed in Figure 4a. The
420 objects defined in the CIM file, e.g. *Terminal*, *TopologicalNode*, *Synchronous-*
421 *Machine*, are mapped to DPsim objects according to the *CIM::Reader* class
422 of DPsim. The system frequency, 60 Hz, is not defined in the CIM file. There-
423 fore, it needs to be specified before loading the CIM file. Furthermore, a fault
424 is applied to node 9 of the imported system. To implemented the fault, the
425 system is extended by a switch connected to node 9, which connects the node
426 to ground with a small resistance after 0.2s. The switching action is created
427 as an object of type *Event* and added to the *Simulation* instance.

Listing 2: Python code to import a topology from CIM.

```

428     # Read from CIM
429     files = glob.glob('../dpsim/Examples/CIM/WSCC-09_RX_Dyn/*.xml')
430     system = dpsim.load_cim('WSCC-9bus', files, frequency=60)
431
432     # Get existing nodes
433     gnd = dpsim.dp.Node.GND()

```


Figure 7: WSCC 9-bus system mechanical speed simulation results after fault

```

434 bus9 = system.nodes['BUS6']
435
436 # Add switch
437 sw = dpsim.dp.ph1.Switch('Switch')
438 sw.R_open = 1e9
439 sw.R_closed = 0.1
440 sw.is_closed = False
441 sw.connect([ bus9, gnd ])
442 system.add_component(sw)
443
444 sim = dpsim.Simulation('WSCC-9bus', system,
445 timestep=0.0001, duration=2, init_steady_state=True)
446
447 sim.add_event(0.2, sw, 'is_closed ', True)
448 sim.start ()

```

449 In Figure 7, it can be seen how the rotational speed of the generators starts to
450 oscillate after the fault. The oscillation frequency depends on the mechanical
451 inertia and as expected the generator with the largest inertia has the lowest
452 oscillation frequency.

453 5. Impact

454 Since DPsim is open source, it can serve as a reference implementation
455 for real-time power system simulators and a common basis for users work-
456 ing with different real-time simulation solutions. Having a common basis
457 facilitates discussions on differences in simulation results of different tools.
458 Besides, DPsim allows for real-time simulation on standard computing hard-
459 ware, making real-time applications available to a wider range of researchers.

460 Thanks to its design, DPsim facilitates distributed real-time co-simulation,
461 which promotes collaboration and allows the use of the simulation capacity
462 of geographically distributed laboratories to support large scale scenarios
463 [5]. Distributed real-time co-simulation allows also for better data privacy,

464 enabling cooperation because, in a co-simulation, each entity can keep its
465 data confidential and only exchange boundary variables. This could be in-
466 teresting for confidential grid data but also black box device models where
467 manufacturers cannot share implementation details.

468 The dynamic phasor approach is used here in a system level simulation
469 in contrast to component level power electronics applications as in [1]. With
470 an increasing share of power electronics in power systems, this approach
471 supports the investigation of future grids.

472 DPsim is already used in the EU H2020 research project RESERVE [29]
473 and it was developed as a solution to decrease the difference between commu-
474 nication delay and simulation time step in previous co-simulation projects,
475 e.g. RT-Superlab [2]. DPsim is promoted by the FEIN association that also
476 hosts its code and documentation [23].

477 **6. Conclusions**

478 The presented software project, DPsim, exploits the dynamic phasor ap-
479 proach to overcome the requirement for EMT simulation that the simulation
480 time step needs to be proportional to the highest signal frequency. In doing
481 so, DPsim facilitates distributed real-time simulation and lets users exploit
482 simulation resources in different geographical locations. For this purpose,
483 DPsim is programmed in the C++ language and has its own MNA based
484 network solver. Despite having a C++ core, the DPsim allows for script-
485 ing simulations via the python interface and reading grid topologies in the
486 standard CIM format via the CIM++ library. These features are demon-
487 strated in two simulation examples, a circuit and a grid simulation. Like-
488 wise, the computational correctness of DPsim and its real-time performance
489 are demonstrated by means of simulation examples. Furthermore, DPsim is
490 tightly integrated with the VILLASframework that offers many interfaces to
491 commercial real-time simulators and hardware.

492 **Acknowledgements**

493 This work was partly funded by the European Unions Horizon 2020
494 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement
495 no 727481.

496 **References**

- 497 [1] S. R. Sanders, J. M. Noworolski, X. Z. Liu, G. C. Verghese, Generalized
498 averaging method for power conversion circuits, *IEEE Transactions on*
499 *Power Electronics* 6 (2) (1991) 251–259.

- 500 [2] A. Monti, M. Stevic, S. Vogel, R. W. De Doncker, E. Bompard, A. Esteb-
501 sari, F. Profumo, R. Hovsapian, M. Mohanpurkar, J. D. Flicker, et al., A
502 global real-time superlab: Enabling high penetration of power electron-
503 ics in the electric grid, *IEEE Power Electronics Magazine* 5 (3) (2018)
504 35–44.
- 505 [3] J. E. Schutt-Ainé, Latency insertion method (lim) for the fast transient
506 simulation of large networks, *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Sys-
507 tems I: Fundamental Theory and Applications* 48 (1) (2001) 81–89.
- 508 [4] M. Stevic, A. Monti, A. Benigni, Development of a simulator-to-
509 simulator interface for geographically distributed simulation of power
510 systems in real time, in: *Industrial Electronics Society, IECON 2015-
511 41st Annual Conference of the IEEE, IEEE, 2015, pp. 005020–005025.*
- 512 [5] M. Mirz, A. Estebarsari, F. Arrigo, E. Bompard, A. Monti, Dynamic
513 phasors to enable distributed real-time simulation, in: *Clean Electrical
514 Power (ICCEP), 2017 6th International Conference on, IEEE, 2017, pp.
515 139–144.*
- 516 [6] S. Vogel, M. Mirz, L. Razik, A. Monti, An open solution for next-
517 generation real-time power system simulation, in: *Energy Internet and
518 Energy System Integration (EI2), 2017 IEEE Conference on, IEEE,
519 2017, pp. 1–6.*
- 520 [7] M. Mirz, S. Vogel, A. Monti, First interconnection test of the nodes in
521 pan-european simulation platform, *RESERVE Library* (2017).
- 522 [8] W. Braun, F. Casella, B. Bachmann, et al., Solving large-scale modelica
523 models: new approaches and experimental results using openmodelica,
524 in: *12 International Modelica Conference, Linköping University Elec-
525 tronic Press, 2017, pp. 557–563.*
- 526 [9] A. Guironnet, M. Saugier, S. Petitrenaud, F. Xavier, P. Panciatici, To-
527 wards an open-source solution using modelica for time-domain simu-
528 lation of power systems, in: *2018 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid
529 Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT-Europe), IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–6.*
- 530 [10] F. Casella, A. Leva, A. Bartolini, Simulation of large grids in openmod-
531 elica: reflections and perspectives, in: *Proceedings of the 12th Interna-
532 tional Modelica Conference, Prague, Czech Republic, May 15-17, 2017,
533 no. 132, Linköping University Electronic Press, 2017, pp. 227–233.*

- 534 [11] M. Baudette, M. Castro, T. Rabuzin, J. Lavenius, T. Bogodorova,
535 L. Vanfretti, Openipsl: Open-instance power system libraryupdate 1.5
536 to itesla power systems library (ipsl): A modelica library for phasor
537 time-domain simulations, *SoftwareX* 7 (2018) 34–36.
- 538 [12] A. T. Martí, J. Jatskevich, Transient stability analysis using shifted fre-
539 quency analysis (sfa), in: 2018 Power Systems Computation Conference
540 (PSCC), IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- 541 [13] T. Demiray, G. Andersson, L. Busarello, Evaluation study for the sim-
542 ulation of power system transients using dynamic phasor models, in:
543 Transmission and Distribution Conference and Exposition: Latin Amer-
544 ica, 2008 IEEE/PES, IEEE, 2008, pp. 1–6.
- 545 [14] J. R. Martí, H. W. Dommel, B. D. Bonatto, A. F. Barrete, Shifted
546 frequency analysis (SFA) concepts for EMTP modelling and simulation
547 of power system dynamics, in: Power Systems Computation Conference
548 (PSCC), 2014, IEEE, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- 549 [15] K. Strunz, R. Shintaku, F. Gao, Frequency-adaptive network modeling
550 for integrative simulation of natural and envelope waveforms in power
551 systems and circuits, *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I:
552 Regular Papers* 53 (12) (2006) 2788–2803.
- 553 [16] A. Suárez, Analysis and design of autonomous microwave circuits, Vol.
554 190, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- 555 [17] J. G. Proakis, Digital communications. 1995.
- 556 [18] Energy management system application program interface (EMS-API)
557 - part 301: Common information model (CIM) base, Standard, Interna-
558 tional Electrotechnical Commission (2016).
- 559 [19] FEIN Aachen e. V., VILLAS Framework (Accessed 2018-11-23).
560 URL <http://www.fein-aachen.org/projects/villas-framework>
- 561 [20] G. Guennebaud, B. Jacob, et al., Eigen v3, <http://eigen.tuxfamily.org>
562 (2010).
- 563 [21] A. C. Hindmarsh, P. N. Brown, K. E. Grant, S. L. Lee, R. Serban, D. E.
564 Shumaker, C. S. Woodward, SUNDIALS: Suite of nonlinear and differ-
565 ential/algebraic equation solvers, *ACM Transactions on Mathematical
566 Software (TOMS)* 31 (3) (2005) 363–396.

- 567 [22] L. Razik, M. Mirz, D. Knibbe, S. Lankes, A. Monti, Automated dese-
568 rializer generation from CIM ontologies: CIM++ - an easy-to-use and
569 automated adaptable open-source library for object deserialization in
570 C++ from documents based on user-specified UML models following
571 the common information model (CIM) standards for the energy sector,
572 Computer Science-Research and Development 33 (1-2) (2018) 93–103.
- 573 [23] FEIN Aachen e. V., DPsim (Accessed 2018-11-23).
574 URL <https://www.fein-aachen.org/projects/dpsim/>
- 575 [24] M. Walther, V. Waurich, C. Schubert, I. Gubsch, Equation based paral-
576 lelization of modelica models, in: Proceedings of the 10th International
577 Modelica Conference, March 10-12, 2014, Lund, Sweden, pp. 1213–1220.
- 578 [25] N. Watson, J. Arrillaga, Power Systems Electromagnetic Transients Sim-
579 ulation, IET, 2003.
- 580 [26] Red Hat Enterprise Linux for Real Time 7: Tuning Guide (Oct. 2018).
581 URL [https://access.redhat.com/documentation/en-us/red_hat_enterprise_linux_for](https://access.redhat.com/documentation/en-us/red_hat_enterprise_linux_for_real_time/7/html/tuning_guide/)
- 582 [27] P. Zhang, J. R. Marti, H. W. Dommel, Synchronous machine model-
583 ing based on shifted frequency analysis, IEEE Transactions on Power
584 Systems 22 (3) (2007) 1139–1147.
- 585 [28] P. Kundur, N. J. Balu, M. G. Lauby, Power system stability and control,
586 Vol. 7, McGraw-hill New York, 1994.
- 587 [29] RESERVE (Accessed 2018-11-23).
588 URL <http://www.re-serve.eu/>

589 **Required Metadata**

590 **Current code version**

591 **Current executable software version**

Nr.	Code metadata description	Please fill in this column
C1	Current code version	v1.0.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/simulation/dpsim/tags/v1.0.0
C3	Legal Code License	GPLv3
C4	Code versioning system used	git
C5	Software code languages, tools, and services used	C++, python
C6	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	DPsim can be compiled for Linux, OSX and Windows. The main dependencies are: gcc, Eigen, Python, CIM++, VILLASnode, Sundials. A Dockerfile with all dependencies is included in the repository.
C7	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://fein-aachen.org/projects/dpsim/
C8	Support email for questions	mmirz@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de

Table 1: Code metadata (mandatory)

Nr.	(Executable) software metadata description	Please fill in this column
S1	Current software version	v1.0.0
S2	Permanent link to executables of this version	https://hub.docker.com/r/rwthacs/dpsim
S3	Legal Software License	GPLv3
S4	Computing platforms/Operating Systems	Linux docker container
S5	Installation requirements & dependencies	Only a docker installation is required.
S6	If available, link to user manual	https://fein-aachen.org/projects/dpsim/
S7	Support email for questions	mmirz@eonerc.rwth-aachen.de

Table 2: Software metadata (optional)